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Research Article

**OBSERVATION OF THE ROLE OF THE GENES IN THE
CHILD AND DETERMINATION OF THE CHANCE OF TYPE 1
DIABETES**¹Dr. Ayesha Sajjad, ²Dr Sadaf Aslam, ³Dr Amna Mahmood¹Mayo Hospital Lahore²BHU Saroop Wala Hafizabad³Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

The type 1 diabetes is a type of diabetes in patient has high sugar and glucose level. It comes in studies that the children whose parents or grandparents or above have the form 1 diabetes. It is observed that the children who are from form 1 diabetes have 11 percent more chances of diabetes then of other children. We compared the children from form 1 diabetes from the normal children it is observed that he has 11 percent more chances of have diabetes then a normal population or children. It is observing that the genes of parents and grandparents plays a very important role in progression of diabetes. It is decided from the genes of parents that the child has diabetes or not. Diabetes 1 is a type of diabetes with it is due to the destruction of beta cells. It is observed that the patients have the islet auto antibody is a strong impact by hla and have the small participation then the others people genes.

KEYWORDS: Form 1 diabetes, role of genes, parents are from diabetes background, normal patients, the islet auto anti body, normal population, 11 percent more chances.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is a type of disease in which patient have the higher level of sugar and glucose [1]. There is two auto antibodies that is involved in form 1 diabetes is anti-gad and anti ia2. It is observed that these two auto antibodies is responsible for the destruction of beta cells and destruction of beta cells responsible for proper observance of glucose [2]. The purpose of this study is to find that the what a gene play a role in divergence in form 1 diabetes [3]. And what genes play a role in general families and affected families with form 1 diabetes [4]. During this study it is observed that the child from the affected by form 1 diabetes have a very higher risk of that they must be a chance of 11 percent more to have diabetes in future. It is important to find that difference of genetic between the normal population and the children have from the form 1 diabetes back ground. To find this we have to find the genetic differences between we have to use paradigms [5]. It is also important to observe that the two factors effect on this form 1 diabetes [6]. The two important factors are environmental factor and the genetic factor [7]. The environmental factor also plays an important role in the progression of form 2 diabetes [8]. It is observed that about of 500000 new born have the higher risks of diabetes [9]. It is observed that the child from normal family and from the form 2 background had a very low chance or by chance to building a islet auto antibody [10]. Observed that the child from normal family and from the form 2 background had a very low chance or by chance to building an islet auto antibody [11].

METHODOLOGY:

For this study or for this purpose we performed a study in mayo hospital. We have the children of 9000 that are from form 1 diabetes patients it means that the 9000 children in their family their parents and their family members have the form 1 diabetes the form 1 diabetes have in may be their parents and may be their grandparents and may be in their above. These children had stayed in the mayo hospital

Lahore. It is must be included in eye that the one sample of blood must take after the birth we used different analysis methods and other tests in this study. It is observed that the method called snp analysis it is performed by using immune chip. These proper results must be obtained due to the 40 snp analysis after that the we combined the all the result in one place. It is observed that the with after every 4 months. It is also observed that the test will be conducted 5 years consecutive. Then the result of auto antibodies had been combined in one file. We obtained the positive result in this respective.

RESULTS:

The following result had been obtained that the normal patients without the form 1 diabetes in their child there is a very rare chance of have diabetes. But one of the patients who are belong from the form 1 background have the higher the risk of have diabetes in their child. It is observed that the ISLET auto antibody have present in or born in the patients and have the ability to maximizes this auto antibodies. According to the following figure it is shows that the according to the sex country and the patient are from the first degree relative and the what is happening next. We also observed that the genetic risk in this study it is observed that the children are from the form 1 diabetes back ground have a very higher risk of the form 1 diabetes. It is also observed that the parents have same genetic risk also increases the chance of the form 1 diabetes. It is also observed that the patients have the frequencies have been increased in the patients from the form 1 diabetes. It is a very rare chance in mayo hospital Lahore that this study had been performed and this type of data compared with each other. It is also observed that the patients have higher risk of diabetes background also their childs have the higher chance of have of form 1 diabetes. We also have to find that the genetic view it is observed that the meier analyysics of the children that have from the healthy background we have performed the Kaplan confounder on their family background to access the how many chances have the child to have form 1 diabetes. The genetic risk score and others factors as shown in the following figure.

Table 1 – Study characteristics by first-degree relative status

Variable	FDR children (<i>n</i> = 423)	GP children (<i>n</i> = 4,149)
Males	200 (47.3)	2,082 (50.2)
HLA genotype		
<i>DR3/4-DQ8</i>	280 (66.2)	2,755 (66.4)
<i>DR4-DQ8/DR4-DQ8</i>	143 (33.8)	1,394 (33.6)
Country		
U.S.	194 (45.9)	1,750 (42.2)
Finland	51 (12.1)	792 (19.1)
Germany	92 (21.7)	209 (5.0)
Sweden	86 (20.3)	1,398 (33.7)
First-degree relative with T1D		
None	0 (0.0)	4,149 (100.0)
Mother	146 (34.5)	0 (0.0)
Father	180 (42.6)	0 (0.0)
Sibling	79 (18.7)	0 (0.0)
Multiplex	18 (4.3)	0 (0.0)
Outcome events		
One or more islet autoantibodies	85 (20.1)	415 (10.0)
Multiple islet autoantibodies	69 (16.3)	255 (6.1)
First-appearing IAA	51 (12.1)	227 (5.5)
First-appearing GADA	46 (10.9)	250 (6.0)
Diabetes	47 (11.1)	145 (3.5)
Genetic risk score available	408 (96.5)	4,006 (96.6)

Data are *n* (%).

DISCUSSION:

It is observed that the risk of islet auto antibody increase at its peak value due to the effeteness of another auto antibodies [12]. It is also observed that the chances of the type 1 diabetes have increases in the child have from the type 1 diabetes background it is also observed that the how the genes of a parents or a grand parents effects on it [13]. It is also observed

that the parents have same genetic risk also increases the chance of the form 1 diabetes [14]. It is also observed that the patients have the frequencies have been increased in the patients from the form 1 diabetes [15].In the following figure it shows with the age of a child its status is it from diseased background or not [16]. Or according to the increasing of a islet auto antibody as shown in

following figure [17].In children we mostly see type 1 diabetes [18]. Some time diabetes occur due to over eating of fast food [19]. To eat healthy food and take

proper diet is good to save ourselves from diabetes [20].

CONCLUSION:

It is shown in above studied that how genes effect on the type 2 diabetes and how it effects on it. It is also observed that the child with the form 1 diabetes background have the higher risk of have high diabetes in future. We performed a experiment in mayo hospital Lahore. It is in touch with that we performed this study on the 50000 child in which half of them are the type 1 diabetes background and other

are from the healthy background it is observed that the child from the form 1 diabetes background have the 11 percent have more chances of have form 1 diabetes in future. It is also observed that the how the genes of a parents or grandparents gave the new face to this study. We used the methods called the Meta analysis in which we analyzed or merged the different data. We take the sample of child after the birth and also taken the sample after every 3 months.

We take the result after the every three months it is also taken consecutive for the 5 years then we applied the method called the Meta analysis on it and combined the data in a one file. The result and summary of this study is to that the children have from the diabetes background had the more chances of diabetes then the normal individuals .

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